

DIVINFOOD

Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based food

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Novel approach of business models

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Executive summary

This Deliverable examines how innovative business models can embed agrobiodiversity into economically viable food value chains, focusing on Neglected and Underutilised Crops (NUCs) within the DIVINFOOD project. Drawing on data collected from 170 stakeholders across nine Living Labs in seven European countries and building on the GxE (Genotype × Environment) database developed in the project, the report analyses how farmers and small-scale processors integrate NUCs into their Business Model Canvases (BMCs), and how retailers support these upstream actors. This report highlights the interdependence of business models along the value chain and the importance of supportive regulatory frameworks and public funding. The findings demonstrate that the valorisation of NUCs is not the result of isolated firm-level innovation, but of co-constructed strategies that align economic viability with biodiversity conservation and social value creation.

The analysis shows that both farmers and processors construct value propositions that combine economic, environmental, and social dimensions. Farmers frame NUCs primarily as agroecological assets that enhance production resilience, reduce input dependency, and support diversification strategies. Their business model innovations include shared machinery (e.g., CUMAs), informal and trust-based contracts, direct marketing, crop diversification, and value addition through on-farm processing. These strategies mitigate risk and compensate for the relatively small share of land and turnover dedicated to NUCs. Processors, by contrast, position NUCs as differentiated food ingredients and narrative carriers. They translate agronomic and environmental qualities into product attributes such as traceability, health benefits, digestibility, and local identity. Technological adaptation—such as stone milling, slow processing, flexible packaging, and recipe innovation—emerges as a key lever. At the same time, processors manage supply risks through close relationships with farmers, flexible specifications, and product diversification strategies. Retailers play a crucial market-building role by incorporating NUCs into their value proposition, educating consumers, legitimising price premiums, and stabilising demand. Across the chain, direct linkages, trust-based relationships, and short supply chains are central innovations that reconfigure partnerships and redistribute risks and benefits.

1. Introduction

The importance of operating to include sustainability aspects within the activities of businesses is now well established in the world of business management (Hitchcock & Willard, 2006; Joyce & Paquin, 2016). Referred to as “the triple bottom line”¹, and conforming to the three “classic” pillars of sustainability, making a business more sustainable means “improving an organisation’s environmental, social and economic performance” (Hitchcock & Willard, 2006). *How to do so* however, without generating stark trade-offs between the three desirable bottom lines, is a key question. In other words, how a business can “stay in business” and at the same time generate environmental and social welfare is a question that is still today central for researchers and business practitioners alike.

Enhancing agrobiodiversity is fundamental for sustainable food systems because it supports ecological resilience, diversifies nutritional outputs, and strengthens socio-cultural ties within localised food networks, creating a broader base of value, beyond yield and income (Scaramuzzi et al, 2021; FAO 2017). Agrobiodiversity management across supply chain nodes has been shown to open opportunities for integrating biodiversity into business strategies, motivating firms to adopt practices that align ecological and economic goals throughout the chain. The integration of new approaches can stimulate the development of innovative business models that capture multiple dimensions of sustainability, embedding biodiversity conservation into value creation and delivery (Verza et al., 2025).

One of the aims of the DIVINFOOD project is to contribute to answering the question of how to embed and manage agrobiodiversity in business models in innovative ways to support farmers and small-scale processors using diversified crops. It would do so by working with, and closely observing, the work done by the farmers, small processors and retailers that form part of its 9 Living Labs (LLs). Indeed, within its overall goal of “facilitating the use and increasing the value of Neglected and Underutilised Crops (NUCs) in food chains”, one of its specific objectives is that of demonstrating new business models that diversify income and activities for farmers and small-scale processors who use agrobiodiversity, and Work Package 5 (“Co-constructing business models [...] to support biodiversity use in value-based chains [...]”) is the locus of this work. **This Deliverable aims to examine the types of innovations introduced by the businesses involved in DIVINFOOD—particularly farmers and small-scale processors—to ensure economic viability while simultaneously generating environmental and social benefits through the valorisation of NUCs. Specifically, we ask: what business model innovations and strategic approaches do these actors adopt to successfully integrate and market NUCs?**

As mentioned above, the work of DIVINFOOD rests on 9 LLs operating in 7 different countries, each of which focuses on legumes and/or minor cereals underutilised in their countries (see Table 1 below). In line with its multi-actor and participatory approach, the project’s LLs are made up of “quadruple helix” actors, i.e. they include researchers, local associations (including consumer associations), institutions (e.g. local authorities) and actors of the value chain. Given the “whole of

¹ Joyce & Paquin (2016) use the *triple bottom line*—economic, environmental, and social value—as the conceptual backbone of their “Business Model Canvas for Sustainability.” They argue that traditional business models focus almost exclusively on economic value creation and capture (the economic bottom line), which obscures the broader impacts a firm has on society and the environment. For this reason, they propose that a sustainable business model must map how a firm creates, delivers, and captures value across all three dimensions, making externalities visible rather than hidden.

the food chain” approach of the project, actors include not only farmers, but also breeders, seed companies, small-scale processors, mid-tier intermediaries, retailers and gastro-bloggers. It is some of these actors – and their businesses – that will be the focus of this Deliverable.

<i>Name and location of LL</i>	<i>NUCs</i>
Bean-Lyon – Lyon surroundings, Eastern France	“Meat bean”
Bean-Cast – Castelnaudary area, South-west of France	Lingot bean
Cer-Occ – South western regions of France	Einkorn, Rivet Wheat
Leg-ItSwitz - Switzerland, Italy	White lupin
GPea-Port - Portugal	Grass pea
Leg-Hung - Hungary	Local landraces of chickpea, cowpea and common bean
Cer-Hung - Hungary	Einkorn, Emmer
Faba-Nord - Denmark and Sweden	Faba bean
Leg-Nord - Denmark and Sweden	Blue lupine, grey pea, lentils

Table 1. DIVINFOOD’s 9 LLs (location and NUCs)

To answer the above question, we use the data collected within the 9 LLs to fill what is one of DIVINFOOD’s core outputs, the GxE (Genotype-Environment) database. This is more fully described below, in the methodology section. The database is also extensively described in Deliverable 5.2 “Completed database GxE and final list of SMART indexes gathering WP1-5 inputs”. This Deliverable builds upon the data collected under Deliverable 5.2 and some of the initial analysis of costs and benefits presented in said Deliverable under Sections 4.5 and 4.6.

Before moving to the next section, a brief note to explain the 6-month delay in the finalisation of the Deliverable. As mentioned in Section 4.4. of Deliverable 5.2, it was more difficult than expected to retrace food value chains from seed to food products from the data present in the GxE database. For this reason, time was taken beyond the due date to assemble and analyse additional qualitative data to better illustrate some of the main trends emerging from the verbatims present in the database.

2. Methodology

2.1 Conceptual framing

The conceptualisation of Genotype-Environment interactions (GxE) in DIVINFOOD is a novelty insofar as the Environment is no longer limited to the Biophysical environment (Be) (soil, climate), but enlarged to agricultural Management practices (M), processing/cooking technologies (T), marketing Channels (Ch), Social organisations (S) and regulations (R) (Desclaux et al, 2008). In addition, the benefits these interactions produce (B) are measured not only in terms of yield and income, as most private agribusinesses actors in classical economic terms would, but also in terms of Ecosystem Services (ES) and other benefits. Conceptually the above can be summarised in terms of the following equation:

$$\text{GxE (Be, M, T, Ch, S, R)} = \text{ES} + \text{B} + \text{C (Ecosystem services + Benefits + Costs)}$$

In the agri-food system, a business model can be defined as the configuration of activities, resources, and relationships through which actors in the agri-food system create, deliver, and capture value, while operating within specific biophysical, social, and regulatory contexts (Stempfle et al. 2025). In relation to agrobiodiversity, innovative business models refer to the reconfiguration of activities, resources, and stakeholder relationships through which agri-food actors generate economic value while sustaining biological diversity, ecosystem functions, and associated social and cultural benefits (Stempfle et al., 2025; Massari et al., 2025; Mattioni et al., 2024).

In our conceptualisation, a novel agrobiodiversity-oriented business model is one in which the use of NUCs, combined with specific configurations of management practices (M), technologies (T), marketing channels (Ch), social organisations (S), and regulatory frameworks (R), is associated with particular ecosystem services (ES), broader benefits (B)—including yields and income—and identifiable costs (C), such as financial investments and labour requirements. So, for example, S and Ch can include possible partnership with breeders for seed multiplication, mutualisation with other farmers (e.g. shared equipment) and valorisation of by-products (e.g. straw) in a circular economy, and R can include, for example, new contracts between farms and local authorities for biodiversity preservation.

Going back to our research question, this conceptualisation qualifies it in two ways:

- First, when we analyse the innovations that businesses introduce to create value from NUCs, these innovations can be referred to multiple dimensions, namely: (agricultural) management practices, processing technologies, marketing channels, social organisations and the regulatory environment the businesses operate in.
- Second, this approach allows us for a deeper understanding of the values that underpin these businesses (in line with the triple bottom line perspective), by drawing on data that capture a broader range of benefits, extending beyond yield and income.

Research on alternative food networks and the field of valuation (e.g. Dubuisson-Quellier, 2013; Varga, 2019) suggests that the strategies adopted by business actors are closely shaped by the values they seek to enact. This insight motivates the analytical qualifications outlined above.

2.2 Data collection and analysis

Data were collected on the variables of the above equation from a total of 170 stakeholders between June 2024 and September 2025 (see Deliverable 5.2 for a full examination of the GxE database). Data collection was conducted through face-to-face interviews that included both closed and open-ended questions in relation to the selected variables (i.e. new management practices, processing technologies, marketing channels, social organisations, regulations). Respondents included a wide range of private-sector actors operating along the agri-food chain; however, this deliverable focuses specifically on 2 main categories: farmers and processors. These categories are not mutually exclusive: farmers are in some cases also sellers or even processors and sellers, while the processors are at times only processors and at times both processors and sellers (chefs are included in this category). Information on retailers (shops or small supermarkets) was collected and used to integrate the understanding of farmer and processor business functioning. For the purposes of this Deliverable, a mixed method was chosen, whereby the analysis draws on qualitative data derived from open-ended responses (verbatim) and also on some selected quantitative data drawn from the GxE database. Overall, we used the verbatim emerging from the answers provided by 76 stakeholders (see Table 2 for a break-down of the number by type of business).

<i>Farmer</i>	<i>Farmer-seller</i>	<i>Farmer-processor-seller</i>	<i>Processor</i>	<i>Processor-seller</i>	<i>Seller</i>	Total
15	13	18	4	14	12	76

Table 2. Number of stakeholders that answered the open questions

With a view to developing a series of vignettes, for illustrative purposes, three in-depth interviews were carried out in June and July 2024 to complement the above qualitative data: one with the founder of a farmer cooperative in France and two with two bakery owners in Hungary.

In order to investigate new tools and strategies used by the different actors to work with NUCs we used the Business Model Canvas (BMC) for its reported capacity to facilitate a clear and simple description of how a business works (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2011). A BMC (see Fig. 1 below) is made up of nine components. Central to the BMC is the Value Proposition (VP) developed by the firm owner/s that refers to the reasons a customer may value the offerings of a specific firm rather than another. Three of the components focus on customers (relationships, channels and segments), and specifically on how the VP(s) is (are) communicated to customers/clients. The 'Key partners' component describes the network of suppliers and partners that make the model work, while 'Activities' and 'Resources' refer respectively to the most important things a firm must carry out to make its model work and the key physical, financial, or human resources it will need to make that happen. Lastly, in terms of value capture, 'Revenue streams' and 'Cost structure' refer to how a firm generates revenue and monetary profit.

Figure 1. the Business Model Canvas (from Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2011)

The variables reported in the GXE database are: M (management practices), T (processing technologies), Ch (marketing channels), S (social organisations), and R (regulatory environment) and were selected to operationalise key dimensions of the Business Model Canvas. While not mirroring the Canvas one-to-one, these variables capture core elements of value creation, delivery, and capture, as well as the broader institutional context in which businesses operate. More specifically, M and T reflect key activities and resources, Ch relates to channels and market access, S captures partnership and governance arrangements, and R accounts for the regulatory conditions shaping business model viability.

The verbatims related to Ecosystem services and (other) Benefits were coded as VP, as they contribute to build a picture of the values that underpin the business, i.e. the reason/s for which the business was set up². The data emerging from the other questions were coded as either belonging to partners, activities, resources or in relation to customers. This reflects the relational and multidimensional nature of value creation in sustainability-oriented and agrobiodiversity-based business models, where economic, environmental, and social value is co-produced through practices, technologies, and institutional arrangements. Where verbatims have been used to illustrate a point being made below, the respondent has been anonymised by using numbers rather than names. The numbers, preceded by the letter S that stands for Stakeholder, have been placed -where relevant - at the end of a sentence in brackets to identify which stakeholder said what.

The section below describes the business models of farmers and processors involved in the DIVINFOOD project that use NUCs in their business. Sections 3.1. and 3.2. are divided into two sub-sections: the first illustrates the VPs of each actor’s business, while the second describes the functioning of the business based on the building blocks of the BMC as illustrated in Figure 1, with an overall aim to describe the specific configuration of partnerships, activities and resources (i.e. financial and cost-related aspects) that leads the actors to fulfill their VP. Retailers are not covered in this Deliverable as they were analysed in WP1. We have however collected information on the BMC of retailers and present it here in Section 3.3. to show how these have supported the BMCs of farmers and small-scale processors.

Lastly, this Deliverable is tied to WP1, and specifically to Deliverable 1.4 “Typology of short and mid-tier chains valuing biodiversity, including SMART indexes of agrobiodiversity use in

² Please note that the description of the emerging VPs was compared and complemented with data collected and presented in Table 4 (“Inputs related to SMART indexes from the 9 LLs”) of Deliverable 5.2 to ensure coherence, as well as with the motivations to cultivate NUCs presented in the Deliverable 3.1 (Repertoire of local farms using NUCs in agroecology).

marketing and data”. The latter focused on the valorisation of NUCs, i.e. in terms of food chain activities, on the sale and marketing of NUCs. As we have seen, marketing and customer communication do form part of Business Models and will be reported below for each actor. In doing so we will describe the similarities and differences with the results outlined in Deliverable 1.4. For the writing of this deliverable, generative AI software by OpenAI has been used for language editing and improving the readability but not for analytical purposes. After using this service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed, taking full responsibility for the content of the deliverable.

3. Results: the business models of farmers and processors, and the supporting role of retailers

3.1. The business models of farmers (Farmers, Farmer-Sellers and Farmer-Processor-Sellers)

3.1.1. Value Proposition

The values that underpin why DIVINFOOD farmers – across countries and LLs – adopt NUCs, whether they be farmers only (F) or farmer-sellers (FS) or farmer-processor-sellers (FPS), are multifaceted. Economic, environmental and social motivations jointly lead them to use NUCs, including both neglected legumes or minor cereals.

From an **economic standpoint**, farmers (F) in particular point out that *neglected legumes* often require minimal interventions, making them cost-effective and less labor demanding compared to conventional crops. Also, the fact that some varieties offer easier harvesting methods and yield levels comparable to standard beans (i.e. *phaseolus vulgaris*), or that by-products can serve as animal feed makes them economically more interesting. FS and FPS also highlight the market potential of neglected legumes: they offer farmers better control over marketing channels and profitability, with rising consumer demand supporting their cultivation, and they can tap into niche markets such as vegetarian consumers. This group of stakeholders also pointed out the potential of legumes to contribute to the economic resilience of the farm in poor seasons, as dried legumes can be stored long-term, thus helping to manage farm risk.

For *minor cereals* farmers’ economic rationale focuses more on stable, quality production with niche market appeal and value addition rather than bulk yields: farmers find neglected cereals economically attractive because they often provide stable yields due to better adaptation and resilience to weather conditions. FPS particularly valued the fact that they serve as a diversification strategy, including opportunities for direct marketing and value-added processing rather than focusing on mere production volumes. Indeed, crops such as einkorn and rivet wheat have higher market prices per kilo for processed products, allowing better profit margins despite lower volumes. Just like neglected legumes they also have added economic benefits like selling

straw, and have good storage properties, although (costly) specialised preprocessing equipment is often needed for these types of minor cereals.

All types of farmers (F, FS and FPS) agree that *neglected legumes* provide a series of **environmental benefits**: they are highly adaptable to local and marginal conditions, making them ideal for mixed cropping and organic systems, and they enrich biodiversity, attract pollinators (especially lupins and faba beans), and contribute to climate resilience by tolerating drought or flood conditions. In addition, their ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen improves soil fertility and structure while reducing the need for synthetic fertilisers, and their strong resistance to pests and diseases lowers the need for (costly) chemical treatments. This last point shows the close tie between environmental and economic benefits that is recognised and valued by all types of farmers.

Very similar reasons drive farmers to use *minor cereals* on their fields: they are valued for their resilience, especially in the face of climate variability, as they can deliver stable yields even under extremes like drought or heavy rainfall. Farmers also note their crops' suitability for extensive farming, dry soils, and resistance to diseases and cold. Some provide effective ground cover that keeps out weeds and helps maintain clean plots, while their by-products, like husks, are useful for mulch and insulation. Low-input requirements and strong performance on low-potential land further support their environmental appeal, alongside benefits for sustainable rotations and reduced sensitivity to disease compared to modern varieties.

From a **social standpoint**, all types of farmers value strengthening local cultural and nutritional values. In relation to the first point, farmers are motivated to maintain agricultural and culinary traditions, keeping local biodiversity alive while educating new generations. In the case of *minor cereals*, this includes multiplying seeds and maintaining the heritage of crops like einkorn – two aspects particularly important for farmers (F). This is linked to the fact that many of the varieties that are used express some specific regional identity (“terroir”) and connect to community pride and heritage. It is however, not only tradition, but also external interest, including from consumers, schools, and visitors, that has supported the revival and appreciation of *neglected legumes*. From a nutritional standpoint, *neglected legumes* are also valued for their high nutritional quality and health benefits, expanding dietary protein options and promoting better nutrition. This is also true for *minor cereals* – there is among all types of farmers a commitment to returning to traditional crops and improving health, as many ancient cereals are recognised to be nutritionally superior—higher in protein, iron, antioxidants, and other microelements—than modern wheat varieties. These cereals respond well to dietary trends, such as lower gluten options, catering to gluten-sensitive consumers. Benefits also include enabling stable, constant flour quality by blending multiple varieties across seasons, avoiding the need for artificial additives.

3.1.2. Functioning of the business

It is probably this mix of values that underlie the farmers' businesses that lead them to make choices in terms of how they organise their business which are different from farmers who only rely on major crops in conventional farms.

New partners

First of all, farms have opted for forms of partnering that allow them to lower their costs. One form of partnering concerns forging links with other farmers, - whether formal or informal - to share

resources. Cooperatives are one important way in which this occurs. In the Cer-Occ LL for example, large equipment, such as dehullers, is shared through the CUMA (Farming machinery Cooperative) (see Vignette 1 at the end of this section). While cooperatives are more formal/legally framed ways of cooperating, more informal agreements are also used: in the Bean-Cast LL for example tools are shared among farmers, or river wheat seeds are exchanged via informal networks. This allows farmers to reduce long-term seed purchase costs: being part of a network avoids dependence on expensive commercial seed suppliers and farmers eventually develop their own seeds, but at a lower cost. In the case of einkorn in the Cer-Occ LL, the Flor de Peir network allows for an exchange of tools and services (e.g. milling, dehulling) among farmers without monetary transactions (i.e. barter), while other farmers pool logistics through joint purchases (e.g., flour sacks), shared transport (e.g. group deliveries), and shared sorting with neighboring farms. In the Portuguese GPea-Port LL, collaboration occurs through a division of tasks with other farmers. Partnering and sharing are also important for learning: many farmers rely on shared farmer knowledge and local groups rather than costly external consultants.

Farmers also forge links based on trust with other actors, such as processors, intermediaries or consumers. For example, a widely used strategy to reduce costs and build relationships of trust in almost all LLs is that of selling directly to processors, retailers or consumers, thus cutting out middle-men. In the Cer-Occ LL for example, one producer sells about 70 tons of organic einkorn flour annually directly to around 50 bakers, bypassing cooperatives. This direct link occurs regardless of distance: the GxE database shows that the buyer was at time as far as 200 km away, as in the case of Budapest city that represents a key market for farmers in the Hungarian LLs. The types of contracts that farmers have with their buyers highlights the important role played by trust in characterising the links between farmers and other actors. Deliverable 1.4 has already pointed out how the proportion of 'binding' contracts between sellers and suppliers is low (probably due to the low volumes of NUCs involved in the transactions that do not warrant entering into long-term agreements). Data from the GxE database supports this finding but also introduces the idea that trust-based relationships replace formal contracts. The data on contracts in the database is very limited (only 13 farmers inserted data on this topic), but it is still illustrative of the diversity of relationships: 6 farmers had a formal annual contract, and 2 had a verbal contract (considered as a moral commitment), while 5 farmers had no contract. As we shall see below, not having a contract with the buyer is a way to give more space for manoeuvre to the farmer to supply products based on the result of the harvest rather than on predetermined specifications. The same farmer can also have a contract (or not) based on the product: one farmer in the Leg-Nord LL for example has a contract to sell lentils, but no contract for lupins.

New activities

The presence of NUCs on farm leads farmers to change their farm management practices, or activities. For example, they leverage NUC-specific traits for agronomic benefits: in the case of einkorn, its rustic nature and straw production helps natural weed control and reduces labour-intensive weeding, thus supporting organic cultivation. Or they combine NUCs with other crop varieties to maintain consistent product quality: in the Cer-Occ LL for example, mixing several wheat varieties balances out yearly fluctuations in quality and protein content without needing additives like additional gluten: this ensures stable flour quality for manufacturers and consumers (S1). The fact of relying on a different set of partners compared to more conventional farms leads these actors to be open to experimentation. When partnering with a processor such as S11 in France for example, who encourages the growth of diverse crops, farmers in the Bean-Cast LL

remain open to trying new crops, such as the meat bean, especially if processors guarantee a stable market.

A common strategy among small-scale farmers, especially FPS, to ensure the long-term viability of their farms is that of value addition through processing or product diversification. This is also true of DIVINFOOD's small-scale NUC farms, and even more so for the fact of them selling NUCs. Small-scale einkorn producers for example rely on making bread or other products from their flour rather than just selling flour because yields are low - processing thus allows extracting more value from limited harvests (S2). A diversification strategy they use is that of offering a wide variety of products (different grains, flours, or related goods) with an aim to make it easier for shops to stock without sourcing from multiple suppliers – this increases shops' interest in carrying the producer's items (S3). The reason why value addition is so important for these actors is linked to a finding already indicated by Deliverables 1.2, 1.4 and 3.1, and that is that for most of the farmers and initiatives involved in growing and/or selling NUCs, the latter only form a small part of their activity. In Deliverable 1.2 we learnt that on average the portion of surface cultivated with NUC species by the LL farmers represents 6-7% of the utilised agricultural area of the farm, while in Deliverable 1.4. NUCs sales represent less than 25% of the commercial activity for more than half of the initiatives. For this reason, making a greater effort in value addition (through processing and product diversification) is important.

Key resources

Producers rely on several key resources to manage costs and either avoid high price premiums or maintain their niche in the market. One cost reducing activity particularly used by farmers (F) is, as mentioned above, that of sharing equipment rather than owning machinery themselves. Another strategy is that of relying on co-products like straw for additional value – either for small-scale use (e.g., compost or chicken bedding) or limited sale: this adds value without requiring large-scale production (S4, S5, S6).

Subsidies from various sources represent another important resource. Most information here is relative to French farmers, whether they be F, FS or FPS. Organisations such as Arbres et Paysages and Envol Vert assist farmers in adopting agroecological practices like hedge planting, while agroforestry tree subsidies come from partners like Agroof (S7). Through CAP Pillar 2, some national level programs offer 20–30% aid for sorting tools, mills, and bakery equipment (S8).

Relationship with customers

Very sparse information was available on customer relations, segments and communication. Most information was provided by FS and FPS, presumably due to the greater emphasis they place on marketing. In the Danish LL for example, a key obstacle to the wider use of NUC legumes is recognised in the fact that consumers are not well acquainted with these products. This is indeed one of the major findings of Deliverable 1.4 that noted the critical challenges of insufficient demand and lack of consumer awareness on NUCs. One FPS notes, in the case of lentils, the difficulty of getting consumers to appreciate the difference in quality and taste of various lentils which makes it hard to compete with cheaper, imported lentils (S9). This observation likely applies to other contexts as well. Working on communication and customer relations is therefore a key activity for these firms who invest in communication to support the consumers to understand that there is a difference in quality. In this regard labelling can help, such as the Danish organic label that is easier to communicate to Danish consumers since it is a very well-known label in Denmark. Another strategy is that of customising the products for specific consumer segments,

as in the case of einkorn, where FPSs leveraged the increase in demand for gluten-free or low-gluten products to make flour from legumes and less used cereals, such as lentils, chickpeas, buckwheat and maize (S6). Chefs are also considered a specific segment: as there is growing market interest linked to global uncertainties, chefs increasingly consider locally produced goods as part of their supply, reflecting a rising demand for local minor crops (S10).

Vignette 1

Business models for NUCs farmers and farmer-processors that rely on farmer cooperatives: the case study of the “12 einkorn grains” CUMA (Coopérative d’Utilisation de Matériel Agricole) in France

« There are no scheduling issues or late invoices. It is a well-functioning cooperative because all the farmers see the benefits. It is a cooperative that was built by them and for them » (One of the CUMA founders)

CUMAs are a particular type of farmer cooperatives born in France in the early 20th century. The acronym stands for Coopérative d’Utilisation de Matériel Agricole which roughly translates to farm machinery cooperative. Thanks to a specific legal framework, these local farmer cooperatives allow farmers to reduce their operating costs linked to mechanisation by pooling not only machinery, but also labour and infrastructure, such as sheds. Today there are about 9,500 CUMAs in France, and we focus on the “12 einkorn grains” CUMA (12 petit épeautres) to illustrate the benefits that such partnerships can make in the business models of single farmers and/or farmer-processors.

The CUMA was set up in 2016 by 12 farmers (hence its name) who, after the dismantlement of a previous CUMA set up in 1982, felt a need for an organizational set up that would help them pool some of their resources. Before creating the CUMA, the founders ensured that enough tonnage of organic minor cereals (at least 50 tons) could be assembled by the CUMA’s members to make the dehulling effort worthwhile. Once this was ensured, the CUMA was created.

Today the CUMA is made up of about 20 farmers, 15 of which are also artisan bakers (so, farmer-processors), and all of which are organic and sell their products through short supply chains. Working only with organic products is a result of course of a regulation that does not allow to work with organic and non-organic products in the same batch, but it is also an important value for the CUMA, which explains why it is not open to conventional farmers. Initially the CUMA had considered certifying itself as organic, but decided against it as part of its cost reduction strategy since the certification process would have turned out to be expensive (€400 per year). Rather, each farmer uses the tools in their own name, and their products are certified as organic under each farmer’s name. This means that farmers remain in control of their dehulled product and how they want to sell it.

It is important to note that the pooling of tools has helped to cut down costs: while initially a kilo of dehulled einkorn costed 12.5 cents, spreading the initial costs has led to a current price of 8 cents per kg as the CUMA grew. Although farmers do not receive any specific aid for being members of a CUMA, the CUMA itself is eligible for subsidies, tax exemptions and favourable credit access: when it started it received 40% aid for the purchase of its equipment, and it can access bank loans more easily.

Today the CUMA owns a sorting machine (that mainly helps farmers to prepare their seeds), a dehuller, and a cargo-lift. The main advantage of being part of a CUMA is that the cost of the tools is shared among several members. The dehuller was purchased 10 years ago for €30,000: this, and the sorting machine, are very high-quality instruments that would have been difficult for a single farmer to purchase, or would have required them to open up a credit line at the bank. To join any CUMA, farmers purchase shares. In the “12 einkorn grains” CUMA the number of shares is determined based on the number of tons that the new member wishes to dehull (€135 per ton). When a member decides to leave the CUMA, they can retrieve their shares.

The shares are revaluated after a few years: for example, if a farmer starts out dehulling 2 tons of einkorn and then ends up processing 5 tons, after a certain period of time they will have to adjust their shares accordingly. In this specific example, this translates into three additional shares, or $3 \times \$135$. In addition to the above, the “12 einkorn grains” CUMA has introduced a new rule: new members must pay an entry fee of €200 in addition to the shares. This fee was introduced to balance the contributions between the founding members—who bore higher dehulling costs for several years to spread the price of the equipment—and the newcomers.

It is important to note that the members of the CUMA are spread across several departments - some travel several dozen kilometers to use it, and the farmer who is furthest away is around a hundred kilometers away. For this reason, an initial idea had been that of setting up a “mobile CUMA”. This however had 2 disadvantages: 1) the dehuller is a particularly heavy piece of equipment, which makes it hard and expensive to move, and 2) given that all the farmers in the CUMA process their own production, they do not dehull all their einkorn at once, but rather do so gradually, depending on the demand for flour. A mobile CUMA would therefore have required much more complex logistics. Which would have entails a number of drawbacks: cost, a carbon footprint, and the need to regularly renew the mobile machinery, making it overall difficult to operate. What this case shows is the way that the CUMA has been set up to respond to the needs of each actor’s business model, and that the business model’s specific set up (for example, the fact that it uses short chains) has shaped the configuration of the CUMA.

3.2. Processors’ business models

3.2.1 Value Proposition

A mix of economic, environmental and social values also underlie the processors’ business models who choose to use NUCs. From an **economic standpoint**, processors of neglected beans and cereals appreciate the visual quality and product versatility of NUCs. For cereal processors, einkorn’s visual appeal – generally yellow grains - is central as it differentiates bakery products from those made from standard wheat (S8, S12). Bakers, for example, explain that they choose it “to give the crumb a nice colour and more texture” and “to obtain a thicker crust,” while millers and researchers describe the development of a flour with a yellow or creamy colour. The versatility of minor legumes – used as meat substitutes in hamburgers, stews and meatballs, as rich protein flours, or as tempeh chips and snacks – is also appreciated from an economic standpoint because it allows to build multiple revenue streams from the same raw materials (S11, S13). The grey pea in Denmark for example can be used for the sweet as well as the savoury cuisine (S11, S20). At the same time, processors stress that these products are not only a privilege for elites: they present them as affordable and “made for the everyday consumer”. Indeed neglected legumes are appreciated as an inexpensive source of protein: in Sweden for example faba beans stand out as “the cheapest organic legumes in Sweden” (S29), and hospitals, such as S30 in Denmark, favor these legumes as they are consistently cheaper than animal protein alternatives. They are also valued for their long shelf life. Consumer interest is also growing, as reflected in surveys from Hungary. For example, cowpea, though less familiar to home cooks, has been successfully tested in recipes by food bloggers and chefs, and is currently available online; its cooking time after soaking is under 30 minutes, making it promising for restaurant use.

On the **environmental side**, processors explain that minor legumes and cereals are chosen because they actively improve the agroecosystem and reduce dependence on external inputs. Some of the processors surveyed are also farmers (FPS) so they are particularly aware of the environmental benefits of these crops, but actors who are only processors seem also to be fully aware and appreciate the environmental benefits of NUCs. One processor for example notes that lupins, like other legumes, have the ability to enrich the soil, capturing nitrogen from the air and returning it to the soil, which make them a form of “green manure” for subsequent crops and fit into an agroecological logic where “nature has a way of doing things” (S14). Other processors link environmental and territorial arguments: the grey pea used to make falafel in one case, is appreciated because it is locally grown, offers “better transparency, less chemicals” and contributes to “more self-sufficiency,” while also carrying a strong local history (S15). Processors thus see NUCs as a way to move towards systems where crops improve soil fertility, require fewer pesticides and fertilisers, support local self-sufficiency and yield flours and foods that they can credibly describe as healthier and more natural. Lastly, environmental benefits can extend to the energy savings obtained by cooking legumes in pressure cookers, which reduces cooking time and energy use.

Indeed, **health motivations** are central to processors’ reasons for working with NUCs, which is why they weave this dimension directly into product design and communication. Minor cereal processors prefer dealing with wholemeal or semi-whole flours because they are more nutritious, and present products like einkorn bulgur as “easily digestible,” rich in antioxidants and low in gluten, so that even gluten-sensitive consumers can eat them. They use mild methods that maintain the health properties of their products, like fermentation, and use packages, like glass jars, that preserve nutrients and underline the natural character of the product. One processor notes how the feedback received from consumers at the points of sale reinforces these motivations: people report better taste and better digestibility and say they feel satiety more quickly, so “a smaller portion is enough to satiate you”. Processors interpret this as a sign that minor cereals support more nutritious and more satisfying eating patterns (S16). Chefs appreciate the high protein content of legumes that make them nourishing food options (S35), while public canteens appreciate the lower fat content and increased dietary fiber in line with official dietary guidelines. Though thorough cooking is necessary to manage food safety risks, which might reduce some nutritional properties, legumes remain valuable nutritious foods. In terms of affordability, they offer an affordable alternative for proteins, and this offers an important entry point for a cultural shift, a “normalisation” of dishes that are not based on animal protein, thus inspiring consumers to try sustainable, plant-based meals at home.

Locality is also an important value for processors, whether they are FPS, or only processors. One processor insists on working only with local products and small and medium enterprises (S17) and argues that “local means traceability”: knowing exactly where the wheat comes from, which plot and variety, and what commitments and values stand behind it. Even bread is framed socially and creatively: one baker wants to “make bread that’s good for your health” while also taking care of its aesthetics with stencils because it is “fun” and “creative” (S18). Together, these voices show that processors choose neglected legumes and cereals not only for agronomic and economic reasons, but also because they allow them to offer healthy, traceable, socially embedded foods that align with their ethical commitments.

3.2.2 Functioning of the business

New partners

Processors develop a series of key partnerships that are essential to making their businesses functioning while living up to their values. A small-scale processor in the LL Bean-Lyon for example emphasises direct relationships with farmers, describing “a real partnership” built on trust and frequent exchanges, where formal contracts are often absent because volumes are small and committing to fixed quantities is risky and costly for both sides. Data from the GxE on types of contracts that bind processors to suppliers are sparse, but existing data on specifications that processors ask from farmers supports a relationship based on trust. A PS in France for example (LL Meat-Bean) that produces canned beans indicates that he does not have specifications (or a formal contract for that matter) for his suppliers since he works with small volumes and “off-size” products, such as vegetables. A chef working in the same LL has very few specifications for his suppliers, the basic one being that the batches of beans contain the least number of stones possible.

Some processors develop partnerships along the whole local value chain: for example, a processor of the LL Bean-Lyon works directly with organic cereal farmers in eastern Lyon, is active in the Organic Cluster Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, and has joined a retail cooperative to secure new suppliers and outlets in public catering, including supplying flour for bread used in school meals for the City of Lyon. S41 also embeds itself in local alternative economies, for example by using a new local currency called “gonette,” which further ties it into regional networks. Processors like S13 and S20 underline their reliance on tight relationships with a small number of farmers who supply specific crops, such as grasspea or grey peas, noting that this dependence brings strong pressure on quality and mutual trust but also exposes them to supply risks if those producers fail or if volumes and quality are difficult to predict. Vignette 2 below illustrates what a BMC based on direct linkages would look like and how different processors modify their BMC based on their relationships with customers.

Vignette 2*Setting a (fair) price in NUCs-based short supply chains - voices from the Farmer-Miller-Baker network in Hungary*

An informal “Farmer-Miller-Baker Network” has recently been established in Hungary, spearheaded by OMKI (Hungarian Research Institute of Organic Agriculture) with an aim to restore and develop cereal landraces in Hungary. The network connects farmers, millers and bakers (and researchers) in Hungary to (re-)establish NUCs value chains across the rural-urban divide. A constellation of small artisanal bakeries has indeed emerged in the last years, particularly in Budapest but in other smaller towns too, with an aim to reconnect with the rural areas and to use mild processing techniques that make the final bakery products more digestible and appealing.

Not all the bakeries use the same business model. Orma for example, is a small bakery (6 employees) situated in a small town in the south of Hungary. It sources all its flour from local, organic cereal producers who use stone mills (farmer-processors). He met these like-minded producers online, as part of a Facebook group called “Sourdough Lab”. The owner uses a good quantity of cereal landraces, and uses his own original recipes to make the bakery products. Flavour and the health properties of bread made from sourdough are a priority for the owner, who decided to open the bakery 5 years ago because of the importance he attributes to the link between food, environment and health. He has a flexible approach with the suppliers – their relationship is based on trust and not so much on a contract, and he produces every day a different batch of products based on the types and quantities of flours that the producers are able to provide. Due to its size, it is not so much the raw material that is expensive to source, but rather the employees and his time. And it is due to the latter that he places what he calls a “reasonable” price premium on his products.

Yugi on the other hand has a different type of business. His bakery is bigger - it is made up of 22 employees – and he has two “lines” of products: one is more “commercial”, where he sells conventional wheat bread, and the other is more “alternative”, where he sells bakery products made from organic and/or NUC cereals made from flour produced using a stone mill. The marketing of the latter set of products is based on traceability and allows him to place a high premium on them aimed at a specific consumer segment. The other products are placed at a “standard” price to cater for the low/middle-income customers of the bakery that is located in a suburb of Budapest.

While diversification based on customer segmentation is thus a key pricing strategy for Yugi, it is not so for Orma, who expressly prefers to set a “medium” price to all products, without creating a “cheaper” line. This strategy has the advantage of lowering the price of a niche product and making it more accessible to a wider customer base thus “democratising” these types of products.

New activities

Processors who use NUCs constantly adapt their products and processes to the specificities of NUCs. One recurring difficulty is matching packaging formats to consumer expectations: a processor explains that larger 550 g jars of beans “do not sell,” and that only after introducing a smaller jar size did sales almost triple. They interpret this as a proof that they must “adapt to today’s customers” in terms of portion size and price (S11). Technical adaptation is another key activity: they calibrate processing equipment, such as grain sorters and dehullers, to match the particular grain size and characteristics of each batch, ensuring high-quality output. Specialised sorting, multiple passes, and attentive dehulling processes are used to maximize yield and grain quality (S19). Processors also face the technical challenge of maintaining high nutritional and sensory quality while working with small volumes and artisanal methods, which requires slow, careful processing that is less efficient than industrial milling. Several processors insist on using stone mills for einkorn and other grains to preserve nutritional qualities, stressing that this milling is deliberately “slow,” around 10 kg per hour, to avoid heating, oxidation and loss of nutrients, and that sieving is done by gravity without air blasts, unlike industrial roller mills (S8, S3, S21). Similarly, they adapt existing recipes, such as soybean miso techniques, for regional legumes like grass pea to diversify their offerings (S13), or using their cereals for bread, cookies, pancakes, and even pasta, successfully adapting recipes for various formats (S8, S22, S3). Processors also work creatively to offer convenience for consumers, such as providing lingot beans pre-cooked in cans, which reduces preparation time and effort compared to dried beans that require overnight soaking (S23). Some products, like certain types of bread, are designed for easier production, requiring less labor and shaping, which simplifies operations for small processors, as well as increases their quality of life and labour conditions (S24).

Chefs, both those working in collective catering as well as commercial restaurants, have introduced a series of innovations in the kitchen - such as new recipes, resourceful menu designs and flexible cooking processes - in order to make NUCs more appealing and accessible. They have for example leveraged the versatility and neutrality of legumes to modify, or adapt, the texture of “normal” dishes - by mixing neglected crops like meat beans into recipes for texture and a neutral taste (S38, S35) or by adapting pasta recipes that contain minor cereals with modified cooking for texture (S39). This has at times meant greater efforts in terms of time - such as that of planning ahead by soaking beans and grains to improve texture and cooking (S35) - but it is an effort which is considered worth it. Some have innovated with new formats, such as bean-based ice creams (S27, S40) and pastry recipes (S17), to encourage broader consumption of neglected crops. Innovations have also been about waste reduction, as in the case of the LL Bean-Lyon where chefs have reduced costs by incorporating beans and leftover preparations into galettes or patties, and reusing them across successive menus (S35). In Denmark, where lentils and other legumes are being “reintroduced”, the use of legume-based dishes by chefs has also helped spread awareness of local food histories and perspectives, helping to “demystify” legumes.

Key resources

This way of working, while it allows processors to remain true to their values and to differentiate themselves on the market, comes at a cost. Cost aspects are important because of the 70 processing companies (FPS, PS and Ps), 46 are micro-companies, 5 are small and only 1 is medium (for the remaining 8 the information is missing). Annual turnover data is sparse, with the minimum data available pointing to 22,000 euros and the largest to 20 million (the medium sized PS). If we take the case of einkorn as an illustration, information from the LL Cer-Occ indicates

that einkorn flour is “a more expensive flour than wheat because there’s so much work to be done on it” (S1), in terms of dehulling first, but also in terms of other equipment: those FPS who own a mill, have paid between 5,000 and 10,000 euros for it, and if they don’t, evidence shows that they can pay up to 1,000 euros per year for rental (S6). The production of einkorn flour and other products is also expensive in terms of labour use: managing the stone mill and making sure the flour does not stuff the mill or working the sticky dough. In addition to that, einkorn flour has a shorter shelf life than traditional wheat flour which implies management expenses.

Public programmes can help mitigate costs by providing public funds for certain firm activities: in France for example, new processing equipment can be funded 50% by the EU, 25% by the region and 25% by the department through FEADER subsidies, reducing capital costs for those who invest in labour-intensive crops (S11) (see Vignette 3 at the end of this section on the relevance of public support). Cooperatives can also work to reduce costs since in France some processors have been able to invest in professional machinery thanks to the support from the Tarn department and the Occitanie region (S25) (see Vignette 1 above). On the production side, processors confirm what previously stated by farmers, i.e. the financial and technical risks of specialised equipment: one farm chose to buy a dehuller through a CUMA in order to share costs and spread risk, because “investing alone in such machinery for a small market would be too burdensome” (S26).

Chefs use a series of strategies to reduce costs, such as incorporating leftovers into the next day’s dishes (e.g. bean patties) or donating them via a local solidarity fridge. Artefacts, such as pressure cookers are also used to reduce cooking time and energy usage. Public catering restaurants, - such as the S42 in France - use structured menu plans to ensure efficient ingredient use, seasonal adaptation, and bulk purchasing of planned items like pulses. Additionally, pulses serve in multiple parts of meals (starters, mains), reducing the need for a varied inventory. Depending on the context, buying directly from farmers or farmer cooperative, as mentioned above, can also be a way of reducing costs as it reduces transportation costs and eliminates intermediaries.

Relationship with customers

Processors make efforts in trying to valorise NUCs. The specificity of many NUCs means that they are unfamiliar to many customers: Sweden Tempe Food for example highlights that faba beans are “still unknown in the Swedish kitchen,” meaning consumer education and recipe adaptation are crucial. S20 in Denmark reports that even product appearance, such as the unique look of organic grey peas, demands active engagement and communication to foster understanding and acceptance. B2B relationships also require time: S43 notes that introducing new products—like fermented plant proteins—takes significant time (often 1.5 to 2 years) to persuade B2B clients of the benefits; regulatory limits on health claims can make this process even slower and more challenging. There is a perceived lack of discussion and recognition around the health benefits of such products, which complicates efforts to build trust and demand among both industry and final consumers. In France, actors working with minor varieties of beans have mentioned the need to create a PGI (Protected Geographic Indication) to support and promote the product, suggesting that without a geographical indication or similar label it is hard to differentiate niche grains and justify their higher price (S27).

Segmentation strategies are core to processors’ approaches. Processor 11 deliberately adapts packaging sizes to urban and rural families, providing smaller jars for city customers and larger ones for those in the countryside, ensuring convenience and matching local habits. They also tailor packaging to recipe types, such as spreads, soups, or stewed fruits, signaling an attentive approach

to both family size and culinary use. S23 targets children with easy-to-bite products made attractive through shape, coating, and cheese fillings, positioning legumes as tasty and nutritious additions to kid-friendly meals. Processors also appeal to lifestyle and taste preferences. S1 notes that einkorn flour is favored for classic, rustic flavors, particularly appreciated by consumers who seek out older cereal varieties. The same flour is pitched for “gourmet pleasure,” seen as a higher-value replacement for wheat in rustic dishes such as bread, crêpes, galettes, waffles, pies, and pizzas. In Portugal, Processor 13 innovates within traditional culinary cultures, adapting regional Portuguese recipes with legumes like grass pea to diversify applications and highlight unique nutritional advantages.

Underlying these segmentation and relationship tactics is an awareness of shifting market trends. Sustainable foods and green proteins receive more acceptance now than in the past, according to S28, while dishes like hummus and chickpea products are gaining popularity among younger urban consumers in Hungary—demonstrating processors’ readiness to follow demographic changes and leverage emerging opportunities. Processors thus combine flexibility in product design and packaging, targeted communication, consumer testing, and cultural adaptation to build lasting and responsive relationships with a diverse range of customers.

Vignette 3*Legal frameworks (and public funds) to support business models of actors who value agrobiodiversity: the case of the Food Communities in Italy*

Food Communities in Italy were established as a legal tool to protect agricultural and food biodiversity, as defined by Law No. 194 of 1 December 2015. The novelty of this law is that it allows a *diversity* of actors – such as farmers, livestock breeders, fair trade purchasing groups, schools, research centers and associations – to forge agreements for the recovery and enhancement of local genetic resources at risk of extinction. Farmers can assume the role of “custodian farmers” that protect agrobiodiversity *in situ* and make agreements with other actors to make the NUCs available for the construction of a value chain. Food Communities were set up to promote actions that protect agrobiodiversity by supporting local production and raising awareness among the population. Specific objectives include the creation of short supply chains, direct sales, local exchanges, sharing on organic farming and low environmental impact practices, support and sharing on seed selection and multiplication, as well as educational and collective gardening, social farming, and recovery of abandoned land.

The Food Community of the Garfagnana area in Tuscany is an example of such a community. It was set up in 2017 to protect the various NUCs grown in the area (the “Formenton Ottofile” maize for example or the “Fagiolina Garfagnina” bean and the “Strawberry” tomato). It started off as a pilot project of the Union of Municipalities under the impulse of the Tuscany Region (initially financed by a rural development project, 2014-2020). The Community was set up around three instruments: 1) a Community Charter that defines members’ roles, and the Community’s organisation and principles. This was signed in 2017 by 54 members (e.g. farmers, restaurants, processors); 2) a pact for food and agrobiodiversity (to involve associations, institutional and research experts), and 3) a strategic plan (e.g. among these was a competition among school students to design a logo for the community). Legally speaking, the Community can be considered as an “Association of social promotion” that aims to valorise and promote local agrobiodiversity. As such, it does not receive any funding and its activities are voluntary: they serve to create a sense of community, to help its members network, and raise the visibility of themes linked to agrobiodiversity.

Since 2022 however, the Community has been registered in a national registry of Food Districts which are eligible for public funds, as are the Operational Groups (OGs) of the European Innovation Partnerships (EIP). From 2019 to 2023 for example, 7 OGs in the Tuscany Region received an average of 300,000 euros under the EIP focus area “Biodiversity” to work on the valorisation of NUCs. A variety of actors were involved, including large retailers interested in making NUCs more widely available on their shelves, local research centres, seed companies, associations such as Slowfood and, of course, farmers. Food communities can receive funds when their members are part of OGs or as members of a Food District.

3.3. Retailers' perspectives: supporting farmers and processors' business models

3.3.1. How retailers strengthen upstream business models through their value proposition

As mentioned above, this subsection focuses on the innovations introduced in retailer BMCs that support and benefit NUC farmers and processors. Retailers do not merely commercialize NUCs; by incorporating them into their value proposition (VP), they actively contribute to stabilising demand, legitimising price premiums, and creating market recognition for farmers and processors.

In line with the VPs observed for farmers and processors, several economic, environmental and social values underpin retailers' choice of NUCs as part of their business model. Importantly, these values translate into concrete support for upstream actors.

From an **economic standpoint**, retailers support farmers by deliberately integrating NUCs into short supply chains. To keep costs low and margins viable while maintaining fair prices, retailers often source directly from producers, or procure NUCs through platforms like S31's supplier network. Sourcing directly from farmers not only reduces intermediaries but also allows for better margins that can sustain local sourcing: S31, for example, maintains a 20% margin thanks to working with short supply lines that require little storage space. This model strengthens farmers' market outlets and provides them with more predictable sales channels. Practical economic benefits also help retailers integrate NUCs sustainably into their offer, which indirectly stabilises demand for farmers. In Denmark, S32 notes that buying lentils for dishes like Bolognese is less costly than minced beef, with similar preparation times. Another retailer adds that lentils are preferable to other legumes because they maintain texture after rehydration and comply more easily with food safety laws compared to animal proteins. These characteristics make NUCs operationally viable for retailers, ensuring they remain a stable component of menus and assortments rather than occasional niche items. In turn, this regular inclusion supports steady procurement from farmers and processors.

Environmental motivations further reinforce retailers' support of upstream actors. Retailers promote neglected legume varieties because they align with sustainable and agroecological principles. Many prefer organic farming practices to protect soil quality and reduce chemical inputs, and there is a strong focus on respecting seasonality (S34). By privileging organic and seasonal sourcing, retailers create market incentives for farmers who adopt these practices and contribute to biodiversity-oriented production systems.

Retailers also demonstrate **solidarity towards farmers** through explicit organisational choices. Sourcing directly from farmers is valued not only economically but relationally. Some retailers resort to a "pooling" of suppliers for deliveries to improve efficiency and ensure local supply, thereby helping smaller producers access urban or institutional markets. Others include contractual breaks in bad seasons to make it easier for farmers facing climatic or agronomic difficulties. Such flexibility reduces pressure on farmers and distributes risk more equitably along the chain.

Beyond logistics and contracts, retailers also support farmers **symbolically and culturally**. Some see themselves as pioneers who help “shape” consumer taste and normalize NUC consumption. In Denmark, for example, retailers describe their role in promoting grey peas as “being part of the beginning of locally farmed legumes” and collaborating with large kitchens that support this sustainable shift (S28). By legitimizing these crops in public and commercial spaces, retailers contribute to building long-term demand that benefits both farmers and processors.

3.3.2. Functioning of the business: retailers as market integration for NUCs

Many retailers driven by this mixed set of values privilege **direct and trust-based relationships with farmers**, thereby embedding support for upstream actors into their key partnerships. For example, S31 highlights its partnership with associated farmers organised into 100% organic groups who actively participate in cooperative decisions alongside shops, consumer associations and salaried members. In this configuration, farmers are not merely suppliers but **co-actors in governance structures**, which strengthen their bargaining position and voice within the value chain.

Trust plays a central role in these relationships. Retailers frequently rely on informal and trust-based agreements rather than strict official contracts. In France, Seller S36 orders from local farms on the basis of a longstanding verbal agreement lasting 18 years, and Seller S37 maintains non-binding oral contracts with producers. While such arrangements reduce administrative costs for retailers, they also provide farmers with relational continuity and long-term commercial ties, which can be particularly valuable for small-scale NUC producers. Retailers in Denmark also emphasise that local production ensures fresher products and, when available at scale, can be sourced at good prices, reinforcing the competitiveness of local farmers.

Although limited information emerged on key activities, some practices clearly contribute to supporting upstream actors. **Voluntary labels (including QR codes)** are used not only to justify pricing but also to ensure stable pricing structures through fair agreements (e.g., Bio Équitable in France). Such labels enhance transparency and can legitimize price premiums that benefit farmers and processors working with higher production costs.

Retailers’ customer-related activities are particularly important in supporting NUC value chains. In Denmark and Sweden, retailers selling minor crops—especially legumes such as faba beans and lentils—face consumer knowledge gaps and entrenched culinary habits. Retailers like S33 and S29 report limited consumer awareness of the health benefits of these crops and how to use them in everyday cooking. For example, Swedes lack recipes and familiarity with faba beans, and the texture and preparation time (soaking/boiling) deter consumers. Similar issues arise with Danish lentils and Gotland lentils, where consumers are accustomed to cheaper imported products and often perceive local legumes as low-status foods.

To address these barriers, retailers invest in ongoing **customer education, communication, and marketing**. Through practical usage demonstrations, recipe suggestions, and targeted communication, they work to increase familiarity and acceptance. While customers show curiosity for local, high-quality legumes, sustained efforts are required to transform curiosity into regular consumption. In doing so, retailers effectively act as “market builders” for farmers and processors, expanding demand beyond niche consumers.

Customer segmentation strategies also indirectly support upstream actors. Retailers note that their typical customers are often middle or upper-middle class, including some less affluent individuals who consciously allocate part of their budget to higher-quality food. These selective consumers—often shopping at open-air classical or farmer markets—may exclude some population segments (S2), but they form a stable base willing to pay for differentiated, biodiversity-based products. Regular customers who cook frequently do not mind the long cooking times required by minor crops and legumes, making sections with bulk legumes and raw cereals viable and diverse (S31). Specific product appeal, such as einkorn flour attracting nutritionally conscious customers (S36), further anchors demand for NUC-based products.

4. Discussion: innovative aspects of business models that give value to NUCs

Going back to the original set of questions we asked ourselves at the beginning – “in valorising NUCs, what innovations do businesses introduce? What strategies do they use to make them work?” – the above information allows us to sketch out a few salient points.

The way we qualified our questions – pointing to the need to better understand the values that underpin DIVINFOOD’s businesses – is important before we try to understand what innovations the actors introduced. In the sections above we noted how all actors are “pushed” by a mix of values that are often intertwined, with one supporting the other – as in the case of the environmental values that at times support actors’ economic values by helping them save resources. In other cases, however, fulfilling one type of value can come to the detriment of another, as in the case of the specialised processing equipment needed for minor cereals that, while helping to work with NUCs, is very costly and can compromise the economic stability of a firm.

In order to maximise synergies between the values and mitigate trade-offs, business owners introduce a series of novelties in the businesses that we here describe in terms of our conceptual framework, i.e. new management practices, processing technologies, marketing channels, social organisations, and, to a certain extent, regulations. Figure 2 below synthesises the main characteristics of the BMs of farmers (on the left side) and processors (on the right side).

Figure 2. Salient features of Farmer and Processor BMs (figure generated with AI software)

The VP is placed in the centre of the diagram to show how the VPs of both groups of actors are similar. As we have seen above, both farmers and processors articulate value propositions for NUCs that integrate economic, environmental, and social dimensions. The differences that exist between the two reflects their structural position within the NUCs value chain. Farmers construct NUCs primarily as agroecological assets embedded in production systems. Their emphasis lies on input reduction, nitrogen fixation, climate resilience, yield stability, and diversification strategies that enhance farm-level economic robustness. Social values are closely tied to territorial identity, seed stewardship, and the maintenance of agricultural heritage. In contrast, processors construct NUCs as differentiated food ingredients and narrative carriers. Although they acknowledge agronomic and environmental benefits, these are frequently translated into product attributes—such as traceability, naturalness, digestibility, and nutritional superiority—that support branding and consumer communication. Health becomes a central organising principle in processors' business models, shaping processing techniques, packaging choices, and marketing narratives.

Notwithstanding the above they do share similarities in the functioning of their businesses. The top box of the 2 columns that synthesise their BMs in Figure 1 in both cases refers to social organisations (S), and here the biggest novelty for both actors concerns the reliance on direct linkages between farmers and processors, and often retailers, so a shortening of the value chains. This finding is certainly not new, as Deliverable 1.4 had already indicated that most initiatives that valorise NUCs are part of short value chains, and specifically those where farmers sell directly to consumers – and the findings from the GxE database point in the same direction. For farmers this aspect is important because it allows them to take up NUCs more easily. Even though on average

small shares of the land are dedicated to NUCs, farmers put in place a series of risk mitigating strategies linked to the specific agricultural management practices they use (M) or the agreements they forge with buyers (Ch), that allows them to integrate NUCs in their farm without destabilising it. The sharing of resources allows them to keep costs in check and to constantly learn from peers and other partners – a crucial feature when dealing with marginalised crops for which less information is available. As for processors, the use of few local suppliers, informal contracts, flexible specifications, and the acceptance of supply risk mirrors farmers' flexibility logic but exposure them more to supply variability. The risks faced by processors are mitigated through Technological adaptation (T), which is the strongest innovation lever in processor models, but also product diversification and menu flexibility in the case of chefs. Lastly, because of their closest contact with consumers, processors are able to create symbolic and narrative value more explicitly than farmers.

An important point to make, beyond the description of the single components of the BM, is how the components affect one another. For example, if a farmer or a processor chose to make a change in their social organisation, this has implications for their business models as a whole: in the case of farmers, the fact of choosing to have a direct relationship - often based on trust - with processors (S) can lead some farmers to experiment in the field (M), such as sowing a mix of conventional and minor cereals, or the willingness to try new varieties if they know that a processor will guarantee a market for the products, or to have an informal contact rather than a formal one (Ch). Importantly this has implications on cost: the web of partnerships that farmers are engaged with allows them to share costs of tangible and intangible tools (machinery but also knowledge) barter (tools, services and labour), and negotiate a better price directly with the buyers. Direct linkages with the farmers are also useful for processors and retailers due to the cost-saving results. There are however supply-related risks linked to the fact that volumes may not match requests or there may be late deliveries, but processors and retailers are willing to take these risks to live up to the values that underpin their firms. And once again, they change certain aspects of their business model to mitigate these risks, such as in the case of chefs that rely on flexible menus to adjust to varying supplies and adapt their cooking times (T) or processors that do not apply strict specifications in terms of what types of products they need (Ch).

The business models of the actors that valorise NUCs do not only change based on new modes of social organisation. This is certainly one “entry point”, that is linked to the VP that underlies the businesses – values of solidarity, of environmental “care”, but also economic considerations linked to cost savings: this is what drives actors to choose direct linkages. There are other entry points however that lead to changes in the BM, as for example the commitment to “mild” processing (T) or the desire to take advantage of rising consumer demands around gluten-free products (Ch). It is changes in these two realms that lead actors to choose to interact directly with farmers who grow NUCs (S). This in turn leads processors to adapt their machines to ensure that NUCs can be properly pre-processed and processed.

What the above shows is the interdependence between the BMs of the actors that value NUCs all along the value chain. As we have seen above, while the VPs of the two sets of actors are similar in many ways, they are also complementary: whereas farmers' value proposition is primarily grounded in multifunctional production resilience, processors' value proposition reflects multifunctional market mediation where NUCs are vehicles for product innovation, ethical positioning, and the normalisation of plant-based consumption. In other words, the business model of each actor along a NUC value chain influences other business models. This is clear for example from the work that retailers carry out in making NUCs more desirable for consumers: as

retailers change their business models to make NUCs more acceptable, this increases the demand for NUCs and therefore potentially the offer from farmers and processors. This illustrates how sustainability transitions around NUCs are co-constructed. It also highlights the importance of considering what goes *beyond* the single business model of the single firm, such as the regulatory framework (R) in which firms are embedded: we have seen how, especially for farmers and processors, subsidies and grants have played an important role in facilitating the use of NUCs.

What this last consideration points to are the limits of thinking of innovations only in terms of voluntarist actions of individual firms, and the need to consider the broader framework that can support actors take up or develop helpful innovations. In this Deliverable we have identified three areas of support as depicted in the Vignettes: what ties these examples together is the illustration of public sector vision and tangible support in the form of legislation and funds (Coops and Food Communities) as well as organisational capacity (creation of a network spearheaded by a publicly funded association).

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